

Neuronal Membrane and Drug Interaction

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IN recent years investigation into the properties of neuronal membranes is gradually gaining importance in view of the fact that CNS is very rich in membranous structures and that the main locus of action of many of the neuropharmacologic drugs is on the CNS. Another important aspect of neuronal membrane in contrast to other cell membranes is its unusually high lipid (about 50% of the total solid) and proteins (about 40% of the dry weight) together with carbohydrates and nucleic acids which allow various neurotropic drugs to interact with characteristic biochemical and physiological changes.

Investigation as to how any agent affect membrane phenomena at the cerebral tissue level has been greatly facilitated by the ability to prepare different subcellular membrane fragments. The membrane structures from cerebral cortex have been well characterised in microsomal¹ and synaptosomal² fractions either by standard conditions of centrifugation or by electron microscopy. Although membranes have been isolated and their components have been studied by various techniques, it is still difficult to give a simple definition of biological membranes.

Neuronal membrane model

Until 1962, the *unit membrane hypothesis* of Danielli and Davson (1935)³ and its modified form by Robertson (1959)⁴ was considered to be universal for biological membranes. At the present time, however, the general applicability of this concept is questioned by many due to the following limitations :

- (i) physical and chemical transformation of membranes during preparation for electron microscopic study,
- (ii) variation in lipid and enzyme composition in isolated membranes of different types⁵. This variation may give rise to different forms of packing⁶,

- (iii) electron microscopic pictures some times show globular structure⁷,
- (iv) ultra-structural details by negative staining are incompatible with the unit membrane concept⁸.

It is now certain that different membranes vary substantially in molecular composition, enzymatic activity, ion transport functions, thickness and in the type of electron microscopic image. The membranes may also change locally in structure as a function of activity⁹⁻¹¹.

- (a) *Lipids* : Each type of membranes contains a characteristic set of *complex lipids* (50-60% of the membrane mass) which are important determinants of membrane properties. Thus phosphatidylserine and phosphatidylglycerol of membranes can discriminate Na⁺ and K⁺ ions in active transport process¹². Phospholipase C which cleaves both choline phosphoglyceride and the diacyl type of ethanolamine phosphoglyceride from membrane lipids produce a loss of about 50% of Na⁺—K⁺ stimulated ATPase, K⁺ stimulated *p*-nitrophenyl phosphatase, and Na⁺ stimulated ADP—ATP exchange activities^{17,18}, although has no effect on the membrane AChE activity¹⁷. Besides phospholipids, participation of gangliosides in the structure and/or function of neuronal membranes has been shown¹³⁻¹⁶.

- (b) *Proteins* : Simple lipid bilayers fail to reproduce many of the characteristics of biological membranes. Thus biomembranes can discriminate the sugars by their conformation upto 10,000 fold, whereas the lipid membrane can do so only upto 40 fold¹⁹. This strongly supports the role of membrane proteins in addition to the lipids. Several physical and chemical studies revealed that

the proteins are relatively fixed on the membrane structure but the membrane lipids have considerable freedom of movement²⁰⁻²³. Recent studies, however, indicated that active membrane proteins may have different conformational states depending on the nature of microenvironment surrounding the membrane proteins. A fluorescence probe analysis of possible conformational changes in the $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$ ATPase of synaptic membranes induced by nucleotide, Na^+ , K^+ and ouabain indicate that in presence of specific ionic microenvironment, ouabain interacts with $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$ ATPase to produce a significant conformational change²⁴. The conformation of membrane proteins have been variously suggested to be in the β -configuration, partially in α -helical form and also in globular arrangements. Membrane models in which proteins in lipid bilayers²⁵ and peptide chains forming cross-links across the membrane²⁶ have been suggested. Although several models of neuronal membranes have been suggested but neither of them appear to account for all the physical and biochemical data.

Outer coat of neuronal membrane : The *outer coat* of membranes of most of the mammalian cells contain collagen, chondroitin or dermatan acid mucopolysaccharides. The membranes of neuronal cells on the other hand, contain carbohydrate rich structures namely, glycolipids and glycoproteins and other components viz., phospholipids—all possess polar heads and are mainly responsible for the electrical properties of the membranes²⁷⁻²⁹. Among the membrane lipids, gangliosides are not merely the structural lipids but play dynamic role in neurofunction. Monosialogangliosides are present along the axon, while polysialogangliosides occur mostly at the nerve endings³⁴. The gangliosides possess negatively charged carboxyl groups of the sialic acid residues which play important role in membrane electrical excitability. Glycoprotein of the cell coat also contain sialic acid and share an important common denominator with the gangliosides. These compounds may extend outside the cell coat and into the intracellular space and are thus exposed to the extracellular monovalent

and divalent cations, being much like a biological cation exchange resin³⁰.

Membrane-bound enzymes

Many membrane structures have associated with them two general kinds of proteins. A complex partially soluble class of protein is associated with the backbone or structure of the membrane itself. The term '*structural*' has been applied to the latter class because they have no functional relationship other than that of membrane organisation. There are many membrane proteins which have both functional as well as structural importance. These proteins are characterised by being easily removable from the membrane and possessing enzyme or enzyme like activity³¹. Various enzymes, viz., ChE, $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$ ATPase, *para*-nitrophenylphosphatase, glutamine synthetase(GS), etc. are incorporated into the fabric of particular membranes and it is these enzyme complexes which are thought to represent the particulate texture of membrane surfaces³².

According to several workers, most of the enzymes are bound in the membrane through lipid or other components. Other factors viz., hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic interactions, van der Waals forces, -S-S-bridges, electrostatic attractions etc., also take part in the structural and functional integrity of membrane-bound enzymes. Thus the activities of complex NADH-electron transport system of mitochondria, $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+ - \text{Mg}^{2+}$ ATPase of the microsomal system are dependent upon phospholipids³³⁻³⁸. Removal of membrane components produce differential effect upon the activities of several enzymes. It has recently been observed that removal of about 70% of the membrane-bound sialic acid by the action of neuraminidase had a differential effect on the activities of Mg^{2+} ATPase, $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+ - \text{Mg}^{2+}$ ATPase and 5'-nucleotidase. It has further been shown that removal of the terminal O-glycosidic linked sialic acid from the glycoprotein affects both the Mg^{2+} ATPase (leading to inhibition) and the $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+ - \text{Mg}^{2+}$ ATPase (leading to either inhibition or activation, medium and low activities being activated and high activities being inhibited) while leaving 5'-nucleotidase activity unaffected. It has been suggested that removal of sialic acid might change the relative orientation of the protein and phospholipids and thus affect the ATPase³⁹.

Studies on the effect of phospholipases and/or organic solvents on the membrane $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$ ATPase confirmed absolute requirements of phospholipids

for the enzyme^{17, 40-42}. Recent studies indicated that membrane phospholipids viz., phosphatidylserine and phosphatidylglycerol exhibit a substantial discrimination between Na^+ and K^+ in terms of permeability rate and activation of $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$ -ATPase correlates with the ability of various phospholipids to discriminate for K^+ or Na^+ ¹².

Enzyme function under membrane-bound condition may differ appreciably from that obtained in the free state. A subcellular fraction containing membrane-AChE shows an anomalous pH dependence relative to soluble AChE when assayed in the absence of buffer in the pH state. When assayed in the presence of buffer, the membrane preparation is appreciably activated and pH dependence becomes similar to soluble enzyme⁴³. Several reports confirm alteration of properties of various physiologically important enzymes during their isolation⁴⁴⁻⁴⁷. There is inferential evidence that many parameters associated with the reactions catalysed by the enzymes are a function of their relationship to other components of membrane. Membrane attachment may affect not only the kinetics and substrate specificities of the reactions but impose vectorial character upon the system⁴⁸⁻⁵³.

It has recently been observed that divalent cations bear important role on the regulation of GS activity. Removal of divalent ions produce a change in the enzyme molecule from catalytically 'taut' configuration to a 'relaxed' configuration⁵⁵⁻⁵⁹. Polyamines have physiological functions in preserving the structural integrity of membrane proteins. Recently it has been observed that polyamines can preserve structures of brain cortex ribosomes⁶⁰ and have protective effect from drug-induced destabilisation of membrane-bound enzymes⁶¹. Changes in the stability of ribosomes under the hallucinogenic drug mescaline treated conditions and the role of polyamines in counteracting this destabilisation have also been reported⁶².

Action of detergents

Several detergents have recently been attempted to isolate enzymes from the membrane-bound state. In most of the cases this attempt has been unsuccessful. Isolation of ATPase from the membrane preparations by detergents or NaI resulted in compounds with higher percentage of ion sensitivity than under membrane-bound conditions⁶³⁻⁶⁷. When detergents were used at a very low concentration which was suboptimal to maximum solubilisation, these produced increased

enzyme activity of membrane-AChE⁶⁸, and ATPase^{44,70,72}. The activation of $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$ ATPase was shown not due to the binding of the detergent with the membrane but due to removal of some of the proteins and lipids from the membrane, thereby exposing latent enzyme sites⁷³⁻⁷⁵. Recent studies indicated DOC-induced activation of $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$ ATPase activity of microsomal and synaptosomal membranes is related to altered membrane-enzyme relationship⁷². Several detergents e.g., sodium deoxycholate (DOC), sodium dodecylsulfate (SDS), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide have been found to remove all the major lipids from low density lipoprotein of human plasma membrane. It has been observed that lipid-free protein has altered immunological properties. It is possible that removal of lipid from membrane produces altered conformation of the membrane protein resulting in altered antigenic property⁷⁶. When bovine brain membrane preparations containing Na^+ pump are treated with increasing amounts of digitonin, several enzyme activities characteristic of the pump are progressively inhibited but not to the same extent. Digitonin : protein ratio just sufficient to inhibit the $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$ ATPase activity completely leave 1/4th of the K^+ phosphatase activity still with the membrane. Corresponding amounts of the ADP-ATP exchange activity and the Na^+ dependent labelling of [γ ³²P] ATP also survive⁷⁷. It appears from various observations that membrane attachment to enzymes are not identical to all enzymes. At present, removal of phospholipid by DOC is criticised by several workers, because under certain experimental conditions DOC acts as an enzyme inhibitor^{44,78} and reactivation of the enzyme by the addition of phospholipid merely represents displacement of DOC by phospholipid at some critical point at the active site¹⁸.

Function of neuronal membrane

In recent years it is well-known that several processes viz., active ion-transport, storage, release and uptake of biogenic amines, energy linked metabolic processes etc. occur at the level of membranes. Studies at the *ultrastructural level* of brain indicated that almost all the changes brought about by several drugs are in some way or other related to membrane function.

Several investigators showed that various pathological and physiological conditions as well as pretreatment of animals with drugs produce alterations in the neuronal membrane morphology and activities of

various membrane seated enzymes^{78,80}. Histochemical studies in the brain tissue of experimental epilepsy showed early neuronal changes involve scattering of ribosomes from the endoplasmic reticulum⁸¹. Action of convulsant drugs associated with the chromatolytic changes in the Nissl granules or the ribonucleoprotein particles, the important constituents of microsomes observed during the drug action in brain tissue, support the view that the action of these drugs is determined to a great extent on the drug-membrane interaction^{82,83}. Several workers suggested that many of the neurotropic drugs produce their effects mainly by changing the conformation of the protein component of the membrane and thereby increasing secondarily the transmitter or ion permeability⁸⁴⁻⁸⁷.

Action of depressant drugs

It is well documented that depressant drugs, in general, inhibit cerebral utilisation of energy-rich compounds⁸⁸⁻⁹⁰, uncouple oxidation from phosphorylation in the mitochondrial system⁹¹ and produce diminished excitability in both pre- and post-synaptic membrane⁹². Inhibition of microsomal $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$ ATPase activity is thought to play an important though not primary role in alcohol intoxication^{93,94}. A good agreement was found between narcotic concentrations and the concentrations required for $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$ ATPase inhibition⁹⁵.

Studies on the action of thiopentone, a well-known ultra-short acting depressant, indicated that under *in vivo* conditions of drug treatment (2.5-5.0 mg/100 gm body wt.), both Mg^{2+} and $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$ ATPase activities of the microsomal and synaptosomal preparations were inhibited⁶⁹, possibly due to the depletion

of divalent ions from the membrane^{96,97}. Under the same conditions of drug treatment, GS activity of the microsomal preparation was diminished, while synaptosomal GS activity was increased⁶⁹. This differential response is difficult to explain until the nature and the role of GS in the synaptosomal preparations are well defined.

Under *in vitro* conditions of thiopentone treatment, inhibition mainly of Mg^{2+} ATPase activity of the microsomal preparation was observed. This may possibly be due to the release of Mg^{2+} ions from the membrane. Studies on the role of adrenaline on the thiopentone induced inhibition of Mg^{2+} ATPase activity *in vitro*, indicated a slight restoration of Mg^{2+} ATPase activity in the microsomal preparation. This restoration is more prominent when the assay system contained $\text{ATP} : \text{Mg} = 2$ (Table-I)⁶⁹. In case of synaptosomal preparations, on the other hand, further inhibition of Mg^{2+} ATPase activity was observed in presence of adrenaline *in vitro*. The result may be explained on the basis of some drugs which inhibited Mg^{2+} ATPase activity and $\text{ATP} - \text{Mg}^{2+}$ dependent uptake of noradrenaline into the synaptic vesicles of brain⁹⁸⁻¹⁰².

Subcellular preparations containing 0.5 mg protein were preincubated with appropriate concentration of adrenaline and/or thiopentone in a volume of 1 ml of the assay system at 37°C for 15 minutes. ATPase activity was measured according to the method of Swanson (1966)¹¹⁵.

The differences in the sensitivity of the two subcellular preparations to the action of thiopentone and adrenaline *in vitro* may possibly be due to the presence of high concentration of biogenic amines in

TABLE I—EFFECT OF THIOPENTONE AND ADRENALINE ON THE Mg^{2+} ATPase ACTIVITY OF THE MICROSMAL PREPARATION OF RAT BRAIN⁶⁹.

Concentration (mM)		Mg^{2+} ATPase activity (μ moles of Pi liberated/hr/mg protein)			
ATP	Mg^{2+}	Control	Adrenaline (0.2mM)	Thiopentone (2mM)	Thiopentone (2mM) + Adrenaline (0.2mM)
1.5	3.0	14.30	15.40	8.00	10.40
3.0	3.0	16.80	18.40	11.40	13.00
6.0	3.0	20.00	21.20	16.20	18.40

the synaptosomal preparation, so that added adrenaline reaches inhibitory concentration to the Mg^{2+} ATPase system.

Action of antidepressant drugs

In contrast to the depressants, antidepressants of imipramine type do not inhibit MAO activity unlike several antidepressants, but they block the membrane pump of the synaptic terminals preventing the reuptake of the neurotransmitters at the nerve terminals so that transmitters remain for a long time in contact with the post-synaptic membrane leading to a more intense stimulation¹⁰²⁻¹⁰⁵. This situation is reflected by an increased elimination of the extraneuronal metabolites of NE together with a decrease of the intraneuronal metabolic products¹⁰⁶⁻¹⁰⁸. Moreover desimipramine and protryptiline increase brain NE synthesis¹⁰⁹, and their stimulant activity upon the nor-adrenergic component of the brain is considered to be the basis of the antidepressant efficacy of these compounds¹¹⁰.

Recently it has been observed that imipramine under *in vivo* conditions has a marked stimulatory effect on the $Na^+ - K^+$ ATPase activity of the microsomal preparation, although it has no effect on the synaptosomal $Na^+ - K^+$ ATPase activity^{61,71}. This may indicate that neuropharmacological activity of imipramine is related to increased cation transport and neuronal transmission. Studies on the ChE activity under imipramine treated conditions *in vivo* indicated that the tricyclic antidepressant have very little effect on the ChE activity in brain. Although this effect is not marked but inhibition of some ChE activity by almost all tricyclic antidepressants appear to indicate that these drugs have some definite role on the cholinergic mechanisms in rat brain¹¹³.

In contrast to *in vivo* results, imipramine under *in vitro* conditions exhibits a marked inhibitory effect on the Mg^{2+} and $Na^+ - K^+ - Mg^{2+}$ ATPase activities of both microsomal and synaptosomal preparations⁶¹ and a stimulatory effect on the ChE activity only in the synaptosomal preparations⁶⁹. The apparent difference between the *in vivo* and *in vitro* results may reflect differences in local concentrations of imipramine in the two systems (*in vivo* and *in vitro*) which may not have identical conditions of ionic environment. Previously it has been shown that mechanism of inhibition of $Na^+ - K^+$ ATPase by imipramine and ouabain are different while imipramine inhibits both Mg^{2+} and $Na^+ - K^+$ ATPase activities, ouabain inhibits $Na^+ - K^+$ ATPase activity

only¹¹⁴. Recent studies indicated that imipramine induced inhibition of $Na^+ - K^+ - Mg^{2+}$ ATPase of microsomal and synaptosomal preparations is the result of destabilisation of membrane structure. Kinetic studies with the membrane ATPase in presence of spermine and imipramine support the view that membrane organisation of microsomal and synaptosomal fractions play differential role in counteracting the effect of spermine of drug induced inhibition of ATPase activity. Spermine counteracts the drug-induced inhibition of ATPase activity in the microsomal system mainly by increasing the affinity of the enzyme towards substrate and in the synaptosomal system mainly by increasing the substrate binding sites directly or indirectly⁶¹.

Studies on GS activity, another membrane bound enzyme showed interesting results. A large proportion of GS is localized in the microsomal membranes^{112,111} and a small portion in the synaptosomal fraction^{112,116-118}. It has been observed recently in our laboratory that under *in vivo* condition of imipramine treatment microsomal GS activity was stimulated, although both microsomal and synaptosomal GS activities were increased under *in vitro* conditions of drug treatment (Table-II). This result may indicate

TABLE II. EFFECT OF IMIPRAMINE ON BRAIN GLUTAMINE SYNTHETASE ACTIVITY⁶⁹

Treatment	GS activity (O.D. at 540 m μ /hr/mg protein)	
	Microsome	Synaptosome
<i>In vivo</i>		
Nil	8.88	1.81
Imipramine (1.25mg/100 gm body wt.)	10.36	1.68
Imipramine (2.5mg/100 gm body wt.)	9.65	1.70
<i>In vitro</i>		
Imipramine (mM)		
Nil	8.011	2.019
0.06	8.844	2.124
0.18	10.590	2.862
0.24	11.448	3.186
0.30	12.066	3.852
0.40	9.040	2.860

In the *in vivo* experiments, animals were decapitated 90 minutes after imipramine injection.

In the *in vitro* experiments, subcellular preparations were preincubated with appropriate concentration of drug (mM of imipramine per 4 ml of the assay system) at 37°C for 30 minutes. Each assay system contained 1 mg of protein. Enzyme activity was determined according to the method of Levintow (1954)¹⁰⁰.

that increased GS activity may have functional implication in the increased transport of glutamate within the neurons and thereby glutamate may act as excitatory transmitter. Previous studies suggested that GS may play a synaptic role in non-cholinergic nerve endings involved in glutamic and GABA mechanism¹¹⁸. This mechanism may also explain the removal of excess ammonia arising out of extraneuronal catabolism of different biogenic amines under imipramine treated condition.

Action of convulsant drugs

Convulsant drugs in general reverse the effect of depression. The pattern of changes characteristic of the state of convulsions produced by any of the convulsants tested are, decreased level of phosphocreatine and ATP, increased level of Pi and lactic acid in brain¹¹⁹⁻¹²¹. Several studies have been made to correlate convulsive state with ACh and glutamine level of brain¹²¹⁻¹²³. Strychnine and picrotoxin produce convulsion possibly through the stimulation of ChE activity¹²⁴. This stimulant effect of the two drugs are also dependent on the presence of Ca^{2+} and this is consistent with an antagonism to an immobilisation of Ca^{2+} at the nerve cell membrane¹²⁵. Lowered AChE activity in 'epileptic' cat cerebral cortex has been correlated with the physiologically monitored hyperexcitability¹²⁶. Recently it has been observed in our laboratory that picrotoxin produced very little changes in ChE activity under *in vivo* conditions, under *in vitro* drug treated conditions however, inhibition of microsomal-ChE and stimulation of synaptosomal-ChE were noted⁶⁹. It has been pointed out previously that microsomal ChE can be considered as 'reserve' while synaptosomal-ChE as 'functional',^{127, 128}. Our observation may indicate that microsomal ChE (reserve) activity was inhibited under picrotoxin treated conditions possibly to preserve ACh which normally acts as a convulsant of the CNS¹²⁹, while synaptosomal ChE activity was stimulated under the same conditions of drug treatment, possibly to dispose off excessive release of ACh at the nerve terminals facilitating transmission of nerve impulse.

Both ChE and ATPase of neuronal membrane play unique role in cation transport processes of CNS. Recently correlation of cation transport with the membrane- $Na^+—K^+$ ATPase and the convulsions produced by phenytoin has been made. Significant stimulation of $Na^+—K^+$ ATPase activity of the synaptosomal preparation under conditions of a high $Na^+ : K^+$ ratio (25 to 50 : 1) has been noticed.

At low $Na^+ : K^+$ ratio, however, phenytoin produced inhibitory effect. It has been suggested that phenytoin produced convulsion through the stimulation of membrane $Na^+—K^+$ ATPase activity¹³⁰. Stimulation of $Na^+—K^+$ ATPase of the brain microsomal preparation by strychnine may be explained on the basis of drug induced alteration in the conformational state of the enzyme molecule as a result of which there is increased accessibility of the cationic activators at the effector site of the enzyme molecule¹³¹. Convulsions produced by pentetrazole did not affect concentration of Na^+ and K^+ in cerebral cortex of rat brain, although activity of $Na^+—K^+$ ATPase was substantially increased. Under *in vitro* conditions of pentetrazole treatment, however, Mg^{2+} ATPase was inhibited. The inhibition of Mg^{2+} ATPase activity may be due to an alteration in the binding of divalent ions to phospholipids within the neuronal membrane¹³².

It may be mentioned that picrotoxin under *in vivo* conditions stimulated Mg^{2+} ATPase activity of both microsomal and synaptosomal preparations, although has no effect on the $Na^+—K^+$ ATPase activity of the two subcellular preparations. Under *in vitro* conditions of picrotoxin treatment, however, inhibition mainly of Mg^{2+} ATPase activity in the microsomal preparation and stimulation of the same in the synaptosomal preparation were noted. An increase in $Mg : ATP$ ratio, on the other hand, restored to some extent the picrotoxin induced inhibition of Mg^{2+} ATPase activity⁶⁹. It may be possible that inhibition of Mg^{2+} ATPase activity of the microsomal preparation is due to the drug-induced instability of the membrane system resulting in release of Mg^{2+} or other ions which normally stabilise membrane structure. It has been well observed that convulsants and anti-depressants affect the stability of the ribosomal particles of the brain cortex tissue together with the loss of H-bonded structure of extracted RNA in the ribosomal particles from the drug treated brain cortex slices^{133, 134}. The present observation may indicate that picrotoxin induced inhibition of microsomal Mg^{2+} ATPase is possibly related to the release of Mg^{2+} or other ions from the membrane-bound ribonucleoprotein particles which are absent in the synaptosomal preparations. This may be one of the possible explanations of the differential effect of picrotoxin on the Mg^{2+} ATPase of the two subcellular preparations.

Stimulant drugs are considered to modify the conformation of the protein component of the membrane, thereby increasing secondarily the transmitter or ion permeability of the closely related lipid

component. This membrane labilising action increases the flow of ions or transmitters with a resulting increase in neuronal firing manifesting as convulsions. Bemegrade analepsis against pentobarbitone hypnosis results when the labilising action of the stimulant drug on the protein layer of the neuronal membrane surmounts the stabilising action of the hypnotic drug on the lipid layer¹³⁵.

Convulsions produced by electrical stimulation of the brain cortex of dogs and cats showed marked swelling of the dendrite (apical) terminals, organelles were found dispersed in them, while subsynaptic structures, typical sacs and vesicles as well as the osmophilic mass from the post-synaptic membrane retain their usual location. The pre-synaptic terminals even with swollen dendrite branches do not change as to the size and content of the submicroscopic structures. Electron microscopic examination of the brain tissue after pentetrazole administration to rats showed astroglial swelling and increased electron density of the neurons and of nerve-endings¹³². The significant increase in both nuclear and nucleolar sizes may indicate that during the action of strychnine, picrotoxin or tetanus toxin some changes either osmotic pressure or permeability take place within nuclear and nucleolar regions, as a result of which water uptake and possibly organic cell material are increased, leading to the swelling observed histologically^{83,136}. It has been reported that increased neuronal activity is associated with histological changes in the basophilic and ultraviolet absorbing constituents of the nerve cell cytoplasm. Chromatolysis and quantitative change in either protein or RNA content of the nerve cell during chromatolysis under convulsive states have been observed¹³⁶⁻¹³⁸.

Convulsions induced electrically or by pentamethylene tetrazole caused relatively little alteration of amino acids, although level of alanine increased and GABA and glutamate decreased^{132,139-141}. It has been observed that seizures produced by picrotoxin or pentetrazole increased GABA level slightly and alanine level considerably¹⁴². Hydrazine, a well-known convulsant, inhibited glutamate decarboxylase *in vivo*, caused *in vitro* a considerable reduction in the level of brain GABA, which plays an important role as an inhibitor of neuronal excitation. Metrazole, on the other hand, produces no change in the level of GABA or other amino acids^{143,144}. Fluoroacetate, a well-known convulsant, greatly diminishes the utilisation of ammonium ions by isolated brain cortex slices. It inhibits synthesis of glutamine but have little effect on the formation of other amino acids¹⁴⁵.

Several investigators pointed out that the possible cause of convulsions induced by electroshock or picrotoxin is due to increased brain ammonia¹⁴⁶⁻¹⁵⁰. Free ammonia in the nervous system is derived from deamidation and deamination reactions involving proteins, nucleoproteins and metabolism of catecholamines. While formation of NH_3 may be the probable cause of convulsive state, inhibition of removal of NH_3 may also contribute to the increase in NH_3 level in brain. Removal of NH_3 through the formation of glutamine from glutamic acid with the help of GS^{151,152} and pyruvic acid¹⁵³ may contribute to the main mechanism of NH_3 disposal in brain.

Action of mescaline

In contrast to the action of antidepressants and convulsants, mescaline under *in vivo* conditions produces hyper-reflexia of limbs and static tremors in rats and rabbits and apparently impairs their visual and space perception¹⁵⁴. Although psychotomimetic effects of some anticholinesterase drugs are well documented¹⁵⁵, mescaline in this respect showed no change in the content of ACh in brain¹⁵⁶.

In recent years it has been observed that similar to convulsants and antidepressants, mescaline induces some instability in the ribosomal particles and makes them susceptible releasing protein, RNA, acid-soluble nucleotides and amino acids. In its action on ribosomes mescaline may exert the same disorganising effect as other CNS stimulants. The action of mescaline on the H-bonded structure of the RNA constituent of ribosomes of goat brain-cortex slices showed that mescaline treated ribosomal RNA has less H-bonded structure than the untreated preparation^{157,158}. Although there is no known relevance of the observed lowering of the H-bonded structures of RNA to the pharmacological activities of mescaline, it may be possible that several biochemical changes that have previously been observed are secondary to the loss of H-bonded structure of RNA in the ribosomal particles.

Action of Delta-9-Tetrahydrocannabinol Δ^9 -THC

One of the most characteristic changes brought about by Δ^9 -THC, a well-known psychotomimetic agent, at the level of neuronal membrane is the changes of membrane-bound enzyme activities, studied under both *in vivo* and *in vitro* conditions of drug treatment. It is well-known that Δ^9 -THC is metabolised very rapidly to hydroxylated polar derivatives in course of its action in the body. Amongst the most significant

changes observed are that under *in vivo* conditions, acute doses of the drug (both low and high) bring about perceptible changes either stimulatory or inhibitory in the activities of the few well-marked membrane-bound enzymes, Na⁺ - K⁺ ATPase (inhibitory), AChE (stimulatory), GS (stimulatory). These changes under acute conditions have further been found to be dose dependent. Quite in contrast to those observed under acute conditions, the chronic doses of the drug do not, however, appear to show any significant change either in its stimulatory or inhibitory effects on the enzymes mentioned above. Another point worth mentioning is that the changes in the activity are most prominent in the synaptosomal membrane-bound enzymes, although microsomal membrane-bound enzymes also show some significant changes in activities.

In contrast to the *in vivo* results, under *in vitro* conditions Δ^9 -THC (2-8 μ g/mg protein) showed inhibitory effect on the Na⁺ - K⁺ ATPase and stimulatory effect on the ChE and GS activities of both microsomal and synaptosomal preparations. Changes at the level of mitochondrial system are not so prominent¹⁵⁹.

The present finding is another important example of drug membrane interaction based on the increased or decreased affinity of the drug and/or its metabolites for the membrane components. Here the drug in its unmetabolised condition being lipid soluble has got a greater affinity for the interaction with the membrane lipids and as such under acute conditions variability in the responses in terms of changes of membrane enzymes have been noted. Under chronic conditions, on the other hand, Δ^9 -THC because of its metabolism to water-soluble hydroxylated metabolites has less chance of interaction with the membrane-lipids and hence no significant changes on the activity of membrane-seated enzymes have been noted.

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